

Clinical pharmacist contribution to the quality of ambulatory patient pharmacotherapy at the pharmacotherapy counseling unit of a tertiary care university hospital

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Abstract

Clinical pharmacists enhance safe and high-quality patient care through effective interprofessional collaboration. This study aimed to evaluate pharmacotherapy counseling services provided by clinical pharmacists, assess physician acceptance of recommendations, and determine their impact on patients and the healthcare system. A retrospective observational study was conducted at the University Hospital's Pharmacotherapy Counseling Unit over a 15-month period. Pharmacotherapy plans of 61 ambulatory patients were analyzed, and therapy modifications were classified according to PCNE V9.1. After clinical pharmacist intervention, the median (IQR) number of prescribed medications significantly decreased from 7.5 (8) to 3 (9) ($p < 0.05$) and drug-related problems (DRPs) from 2 (4) to 0 (4) ($p < 0.05$). Among patients aged ≥ 65 years ($n = 22$), potentially inappropriate medications were significantly reduced ($p < 0.05$). Most DRPs were related to inappropriate drug selection. This study demonstrates the positive impact of clinical pharmacists in improving pharmacotherapy quality in ambulatory care in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Keywords

Ambulatory care, medication therapy management, patient care, pharmaceutical services, polypharmacy

Introduction

Clinical pharmacists have been involved in optimizing drug therapy in hospitals since the 1960s, while their role in primary health care began somewhat later, in the 1990s. Among the first countries to implement pharmacotherapy review

within healthcare practice were Australia, the Netherlands, and the United States (Griese-Mammen et al. 2018).

A pharmacotherapy review is a structured assessment of a patient's medication therapy aimed at optimizing drug use and improving health outcomes. This process involves identifying drug-related problems (DRPs) and

recommending appropriate interventions (World Health Organization 2019; Schindler et al. 2020). Medication reconciliation, which aims to develop a single comprehensive medication list, represents an integral component of a structured pharmacotherapy review. It is defined as the creation of a complete list of all medications a patient is taking—including the name, dose, frequency, and route of administration—and comparing this list with current or intended prescribing (Madeira et al. 2023).

Polypharmacy is common among elderly individuals with multiple chronic diseases. Adverse outcomes associated with polypharmacy include adverse drug reactions (ADRs), prolonged hospitalization, and hospital readmission shortly after discharge (Guillot et al. 2020). Healthcare systems increasingly recognize polypharmacy and its associated negative consequences. Studies have shown that one-third of individuals over the age of 75 take six or more medications daily and that in the past two decades, the prevalence of prescribing five or more drugs per patient has quadrupled (Kim and Parish 2017). Individuals aged 65 and older make up 14.5% of the population in the United States and account for 33% of all prescribed medications, and this proportion is expected to rise to 50% by 2040 (Delara et al. 2022).

A clinical pharmacist possesses the expertise to identify, prevent, and correct medication-related errors and, in an outpatient setting, plays a significant role in reducing prescribing errors, thereby decreasing overall healthcare costs (Priya et al. 2021). Global experience and research studies highlight the substantial contribution of clinical pharmacists to patient care. In Australia, for example, pharmacist consultations in primary healthcare clinics help identify and resolve DRPs and improve patient adherence, with these services being well received by both physicians and patients (Tan et al. 2014). The United States Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) also supports collaboration between physicians and pharmacists to improve healthcare for patients with chronic diseases. Direct interaction among pharmacists, prescribers, and patients is crucial for fostering trust and collaboration (CDC 2017).

In January 1999, the Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe (PCNE) developed a classification scheme for DRPs. This scheme is part of a comprehensive toolkit that includes the classification system, reporting forms, and training or validation tools. The classification system has been regularly updated and validated over time, with the current version (9.1) developed by an expert working group in February 2020 (PCNE Association 2020; Saldanha et al. 2020). The American Geriatrics Society (AGS) updated the Beers Criteria in 2023 (originally developed by Marc Beers in 1991). These criteria include medications and medication classes considered potentially inappropriate for use in older adults (AGS 2023; Kovačević et al. 2024).

The implementation of clinical pharmacy services in outpatient or ambulatory care settings across Central and Eastern Europe remains heterogeneous and at various stages of development (Urbańczyk et al. 2023). The establishment of clinical pharmacy in the Republic of Srpska began in 2007 at the largest tertiary care university hospital.

This milestone marked the start of a pilot clinical pharmacy service that gradually expanded across different hospital departments and facilitated the integration of clinical pharmacy into routine clinical practice. In 2023, the conditions were met to launch clinical pharmacy services for outpatients as well, which is to this day one of a kind in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Kovačević and Falade 2025).

By analyzing the services provided within this newly established ambulatory care setting, this study aimed to assess whether clinical pharmacists' recommendations were accepted by family physicians and to evaluate the impact of the service on the quality of patients' pharmacotherapy, with a particular focus on DRPs using the PCNE classification system.

Materials and methods

Study design and participants

A retrospective, observational study was conducted at the Pharmacotherapy Counseling Unit, Department of Clinical Pharmacology and Clinical Investigations, Hospital Pharmacy, University Clinical Center of the Republic of Srpska (UCC RS), Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina. The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the UCC RS (Approval No. 01-19-184-2/24). Due to the retrospective nature of the study and the use of anonymized patient data, the Ethics Committee waived the requirement for individual informed consent.

The study evaluated all pharmacotherapy counseling provided to ambulatory patient care between 31 May 2023 and 28 August 2024. Pharmacotherapy counseling was performed by four pharmacists, each specialized in clinical pharmacy and with extensive experience in identifying and managing DRPs among hospitalized patients at the UCC RS. Patient data used for the pharmacotherapy review were extracted from electronic medical records and included the following: patient initials, age, sex, body weight and height, diagnoses, relevant clinical findings and laboratory results, physician-prescribed medications (both regular and as-needed), self-medication data (including over-the-counter products, herbal medicinal preparations, dietary supplements, and teas), estimated medication adherence level, and reported drug and food allergies. For each medication, the indication, dose, dosing regimen, and route of administration were documented.

Clinical pharmacists provided professional evaluations and recommendations regarding drug therapy. Potential drug–drug interactions were systematically assessed, and all clinically significant interactions were recorded. Recommendations were also provided regarding optimal administration schedules in relation to meals and time of day. Each patient received a written Pharmacotherapy Plan along with verbal counseling on medication use. The same report was made available to hospital physicians through the Clinical Information System (CIS) of the UCC RS and to primary care physicians via the Integrated Health Information System (IZIS) (Računari 2024).

Subsequently, the pharmacist researcher contacted all patients by telephone and reviewed their medical documentation to determine whether the therapy modifications recommended by the clinical pharmacist had been implemented and whether the recommendations were accepted by the treating physicians. Therapy changes were classified according to the PCNE Classification, version 9.1 (PCNE Association 2020). PIMs were assessed using the Beers Criteria (AGS 2023).

Since one-third of the patients were pregnant women, they were analyzed separately to account for the specific pharmacotherapeutic considerations in this population.

Data processing and statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel® (Microsoft Corp., Redmond, WA, USA) and IBM® SPSS® Statistics Version 30.0 (IBM Corporation 2024). The normality of data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk and Kolmogorov–Smirnov tests. As the data did not follow a normal distribution, nonparametric statistical methods were applied. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to compare variables before and after the clinical pharmacist’s intervention, while the Mann–Whitney *U* test was employed to compare independent groups. A *p* value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The documentation of 65 patients who received clinical pharmacist services at the Pharmacotherapy Counseling Unit of the UCC RS over 15 months was analyzed. Four patients were excluded from the study due to unavailability of data (two due to patient death, one due to inability to establish communication, and one due to missing data in the electronic medical record), resulting in a total of 61 patients included in the study (Fig. 1).

The demographic characteristics of the study participants are presented in Table 1.

The median number of medicines per patient was significantly reduced from 7.5 to 3 after the clinical pharmacist’s intervention (Fig. 1).

A total of 193 DRPs were identified in the studied population before the clinical pharmacist’s intervention. Table 2 presents a comparison of median numbers of DRPs before and after the clinical pharmacist’s intervention across the entire study group (61 patients), the pregnant women group (*N* = 26), and the remaining patients (*N* = 35).

Among the 22 patients aged above 65 years (two were excluded due to death), only two did not have any medication classified as a PIM. In this population, the median number (IQR) of PIMs was significantly reduced after the clinical pharmacist’s intervention from 3 (3) to 2 (2), *p* = 0.01. Table 3 presents all PIMs before and after the

Figure 1. Flow diagram of the study and main outcomes (PIMs – potentially inappropriate medications; DRPs – drug-related problems; IQR – interquartile range; *statistical significance was assessed using the Wilcoxon test).

Table 1. Patients' demographic data.

Characteristic	Value
Subpopulations, <i>n</i> (%)	
Pregnant women	26 (42.6)
Age > 65 years	24 (39.4)
Other	11 (18.0)
Age (years), median (IQR)	
Overall population	40 (41)
Non-pregnant patients	70 (11)
Gender (male), <i>N</i> (%)	13 (21.3)

IQR – interquartile range.

Table 2. Comparison of DRPs before and after the pharmacist's intervention.

	Before intervention	After intervention	<i>p</i> -value*
All patients (<i>N</i> = 61), median (IQR)	2 (4)	0 (4)	< 0.01
Pregnant women (<i>N</i> = 26), median (IQR)	1 (1.25)	0 (0)	< 0.01
Non-pregnant patients (<i>N</i> = 35), median (IQR)	4 (6)	3 (5)	< 0.01

*Wilcoxon test, IQR – interquartile range.

clinical pharmacist's intervention according to ATC classification groups. The most frequently prescribed medicines classified as PIMs were furosemide/indapamide, acetylsalicylic acid, bromazepam, and pantoprazole.

The majority of the causes of DRPs were associated with prescribing and drug selection. A total of 75 causes

Table 3. Potentially inappropriate medicines before and after the pharmacist's intervention according to the ATC classification in patients above 65 years of age.

ATC code	Before intervention	After intervention
C03 Diuretics	17	15
N06 Psychoanaleptics	13	9
N05 Psycholeptics	11	9
B01 Antithrombotic agents	6	5
A02 Drugs for acid related disorders	5	5
M01 Anti-inflammatory and antirheumatic products	5	1
C01 Cardiac therapy	3	1
N03 Antiepileptics	3	3
N02 Analgesics	2	1
C09 Agents acting on the renin-angiotensin system	1	1
H02 Corticosteroids for systemic use	1	0
M02 Topical products for joint and muscular pain	1	1
C08 Calcium channel blockers	1	1
A10 Drugs used in diabetes	1	1

ATC – anatomical therapeutic chemical.

were categorized as “Inappropriate drug according to guidelines” (C1.1) and 44 causes as “Other cause; the drug is contraindicated even though selected according to guidelines” (C9.2). A detailed distribution of the causes of DRPs according to the PCNE classification is presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Distribution of the causes of drug-related problems according to the PCNE V9.1 classification.

The majority of planned clinical pharmacists' interventions were in the prescriber-level category: 81 interventions were suggested to the prescriber (I1.3), and 61 interventions involved informing the prescriber (I1.1). A detailed distribution of the number and type of planned interventions is presented in Fig. 3.

After evaluating the proposed interventions, their status was assessed. The most frequently represented categories were "Intervention accepted and fully implemented" (A1.1)—111 cases—and "Intervention not accepted, no agreement" (A2.2)—69 cases. The types and numbers of all intervention statuses proposed to the physician or patient are presented in Fig. 4.

Discussion

This is the first study in Bosnia and Herzegovina describing DRPs and their causes using the PCNE classification system among ambulatory patients. Our findings demonstrate that clinical pharmacists' interventions led to a statistically significant reduction in the median number of medicines per patient, a decrease in the median number of PIMs in older patients, and a lower overall DRP burden. These results underscore the critical role of clinical pharmacists in optimizing pharmacotherapy and improving patient safety in outpatient care.

In our country, medicine utilization has shown an upward trend, as demonstrated in a study of ambulatory care patients (Marković-Peković et al. 2012), with

polypharmacy being particularly pronounced among the elderly (Marković-Peković et al. 2016). One of the main outcomes of the clinical pharmacists' intervention in our study was the reduction in the median number of prescribed medications. This finding aligns with previous research, although patient populations and settings vary. For instance, a Danish study by Nielsen et al. (2013) reported a similar baseline median of eight medicines per patient, while Bahap-Kara et al. (2024) found a median of seven in a cohort of rheumatology patients with an intervention focusing primarily on glucocorticoid-related pharmacotherapy problems. Different results were reported in the study by Štuhec et al. (2021), which included patients over 65 years of age with cardiovascular diseases and marked polypharmacy. In that population, the median number of prescribed medications per patient was significantly reduced after the intervention, from 13 to 12, representing a 7.3% decrease per patient (Štuhec et al. 2021). A retrospective study among geriatric patients conducted by Ma et al. (2021) reported a median of 10 medicines per patient. When viewed collectively, these findings suggest that pharmacist-led medication reviews are effective across diverse patient groups, but the magnitude of the effect may depend on the baseline level of polypharmacy and the specific patient comorbidities. This is further supported by the established positive correlation between the number of medicines and the number of DRPs, as demonstrated by a Danish study conducted in acute care settings (Nielsen et al. 2013). Additionally, a study conducted in Sweden reported that clinical pharmacists' interventions

Figure 3. Number of planned interventions according to the PCNE V9.1 classification.

Figure 4. Distribution of the status of proposed interventions according to the PCNE V9.1 classification.

improved therapeutic outcomes in 68% of patients, prevented or reduced ADRs in 32%, reduced visits to family physicians in 13%, and decreased hospitalizations in 3% of patients (Westerlund and Marklund 2009).

In this study, the clinical pharmacist's intervention also led to a statistically significant reduction in the median number of medicines classified as PIMs in older patients, reinforcing previous findings in a hospital setting (Kovačević et al. 2024). This is consistent with a large-scale study by Doherty et al. (2025) conducted in care homes, where pharmacist-led medicine optimization, which involved over 3000 clinical interventions such as stopping or changing medications, significantly reduced the prevalence of PIMs among older adults. In Slovenia, among psychogeriatric patients, clinical pharmacists' recommendations reduced the total number of PIMs by 21.8% and avoidable drug–drug interactions by 54.9% (Stuhec and Zorjan 2022). In our study, the most frequently prescribed medicines classified as PIMs were furosemide/indapamide, acetylsalicylic acid, bromazepam, and pantoprazole. Similar patterns were observed in a Brazilian study of patients older than 60 years, which found that 52% used at least one PIM, with the most common being benzodiazepines (clonazepam), proton pump inhibitors (omeprazole), and sulfonylureas (glibenclamide) (da Silva et al. 2025).

Beyond the reduction in PIMs, clinical pharmacists also significantly decreased the median number of DRPs in ambulatory care by systematically reviewing patients'

medications in this study. This is consistent with findings from Edwin C.K. Tan et al. (2014), who observed a reduction in DRPs from a median of two to zero after six months in the population of patients using five or more medicines, those requiring therapeutic drug monitoring, or with unplanned hospitalizations and other risk factors for DRPs. Similarly, Yates et al. (2020) reported a significant decrease in the mean number of DRPs per patient from 2.8 to 1.95 following the clinical pharmacist's intervention, while Lensen et al. (2016) observed an average of 2.3 DRPs per patient. Additionally, a prospective follow-up study showed that clinical pharmacists completely resolved 77.1% of the identified DRPs (Bahap-Kara et al. 2024).

A unique aspect of this study was the inclusion of pregnant women, a vulnerable population where polypharmacy is a growing concern. Among 26 pregnant women referred by gynecologists due to concerns regarding drug use during the first trimester, all were advised to continue their pregnancies, as the medications used were not considered teratogenic. In this population, the median number of DRPs was significantly reduced after the pharmacist's intervention. A United Kingdom study (2000–2019) reported that polypharmacy prevalence in the first trimester increased from 8.7% to 18.7%, even though polypharmacy is typically discussed in the context of older adults (Subramanian et al. 2023). Other studies have shown that 42–83.4% of pregnant women experience at least one DRP (Thompson et al. 2015; Smedberg et al. 2016). A Brazilian

study involving 571 hospitalized pregnant women with gestational diabetes or hypertension found a 63.8% prevalence of DRPs (Vale Bezerra et al. 2023).

The majority of the causes of DRPs identified in this study were related to prescribing and inappropriate drug selection, most commonly classified as “Inappropriate drug according to guidelines” (C1.1) and “Drug contraindicated even though selected according to guidelines” (C9.2). These findings are consistent with previous research showing that prescribing errors and suboptimal drug selection account for a large proportion of DRPs, particularly among patients with polypharmacy and multiple comorbidities (Ma et al. 2021; Zhang et al. 2023; Zafar et al. 2025). Similarly, a recent systematic review confirmed that “drug selection” was the most frequent primary cause of DRPs (Ni et al. 2021). In contrast, Vale Bezerra et al. (2023) identified inadequate dose selection and ADRs as the most common DRPs in pregnant women, while a study from Vietnam reported ADRs as the predominant DRP type in outpatients (Huong et al. 2023). Furthermore, a 12-year retrospective cohort study demonstrated that patient-related factors, such as poor adherence and unintentional incorrect routes of administration, were the most common contributors to DRPs among peritoneal dialysis patients (Tay et al. 2024), highlighting potential regional or setting-specific differences.

All patients in this study received a written pharmacotherapy plan (I2.2) and counseling (I2.1) from the clinical pharmacist. As most identified DRPs were related to prescribing and inappropriate drug selection, the majority of interventions were directed at the prescriber (I1) and medicine levels (I3), with “Intervention proposed to prescriber (I1.3)” and “Prescriber informed only (I1.1)” being the most frequent. Similar patterns were reported in other studies, where prescriber-level interventions predominated (89.1% and 61.9%) (Su et al. 2021; Tay et al. 2024), as well as by Zhang et al. (2023), who reported 50.54% of interventions at this level, mainly “Intervention discussed with prescriber (I1.4).”

At the patient level, the most frequent intervention was “Patient referred to prescriber (I2.3),” in contrast to Su et al. (2021), where “Spoken to family member/caregiver (I2.4)” was most common. At the medicine level, “Drug paused or stopped (I3.5)” predominated, whereas other studies reported this intervention in 10–16% of cases (Zhang et al. 2023; Tay et al. 2024), likely reflecting differences in patient populations.

A key indicator of success is the acceptance of pharmacist recommendations. In this study, most interventions were accepted and fully implemented, contributing to the prevention of adverse outcomes. Comparable findings were reported by Zhang et al. (2023), with an acceptance rate of 85.53% and a reduction in potential pharmacotherapy problems from 45.95% to 7.77%. Similarly, Tay et al. (2024) reported that up to 80% of interventions were fully implemented (A1.1), while only 9.4% were not accepted, most often due to lack of cooperation from patients or prescribers.

This study has several limitations. It was a single-center, retrospective study conducted at a tertiary care hospital, which may limit generalizability to other settings. Patient inclusion was based on physicians’ referrals, introducing potential selection bias toward more complex cases. The sample size was relatively small and heterogeneous, which may have influenced the variability of identified DRPs and interventions. In addition, long-term clinical outcomes (e.g., hospitalization, mortality, and quality of life) were not assessed, limiting evaluation of sustained impact. The absence of a control group precluded comparison with standard care. Future studies should address these limitations through prospective, randomized designs with larger samples, more homogeneous populations, and longer follow-up (6–12 months) including clinically relevant outcomes.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that clinical pharmacist interventions in ambulatory care significantly reduced the median number of medications, DRPs, and PIMs, particularly among older adults and pregnant women. The majority of DRPs were associated with drug selection and prescribing practices, emphasizing the need for pharmacist involvement in medication optimization. Most interventions proposed by clinical pharmacists were accepted and fully implemented, indicating a high level of interprofessional collaboration and recognition of the pharmacist’s role in patient care. These findings highlight the importance of integrating clinical pharmacists into outpatient healthcare settings to improve the quality and safety of pharmacotherapy. Future prospective studies with larger and more homogeneous populations are warranted to confirm these results and evaluate long-term clinical outcomes.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee of the University Clinical Center of the Republic of Srpska, Banja Luka (Approval No. 01-19-184-2/24).

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors’ representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalized human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI. No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

T.K. and M.K. contributed to the conceptualization and design of the study and developed the methodology. T.K. was responsible for software support and data curation. Validation of the data and results was performed by R.Š., V.T.V., M.B., and N.Š. Formal analysis was conducted by T.K. in collaboration with M.K. and V.B. The investigation and data collection were carried out by T.K. and M.K., who also contributed to resource acquisition. The original draft of the manuscript was prepared by T.K., V.B., and M.K. Critical review and editing of the manuscript were performed by R.Š., V.T.V.,

M.B., and N.Š., ensuring scientific accuracy and clarity. Visualization of the data and results was developed by V.B. R.Š. provided overall supervision and guidance throughout the study. All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

The data presented in this study are available upon request from the corresponding author due to privacy reasons.

References

- AGS [By the 2023 American Geriatrics Society Beers Criteria® Update Expert Panel] (2023) American Geriatrics Society 2023 updated AGS Beers Criteria® for potentially inappropriate medication use in older adults. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society* 71(7): 2052–2081. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jgs.18372>
- Bahap-Kara M, Sariyildiz E, Yardimci GK, Karadag O, Bayraktar-Ekinocioglu A (2024) Addressing glucocorticoid-related problems with the clinical pharmacist collaboration in rheumatology practice: a prospective follow-up study. *Rheumatology and Therapy* 11(4): 1043–1055. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40744-024-00692-z>
- CDC [Centers for Disease Control and Prevention] (2017) Advancing Team-Based Care Through Collaborative Practice Agreements: A Resource and Implementation Guide for Adding Pharmacists to the Care Team. Atlanta, GA: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, U.S. <https://www.cdc.gov/high-blood-pressure/media/pdfs/2024/04/CPA-Team-Based-Care.pdf> [accessed 12 September 2025]
- da Silva RM, Lucchetti ALG, Ferreira MEC, Silva LO, da Silva Ezequiel O, Martins ELM, Lucchetti G (2025) Association between inappropriate prescribing according to the 2023 beers criteria and different health outcomes: A 1-year longitudinal study in community-dwelling older adults. *Drugs Real World Outcomes* 12(1): 93–103. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40801-024-00474-7>
- Delara M, Murray L, Jafari B, Bahji A, Goodarzi Z, Kirkham J, Chowdhury M, Seitz DP (2022) Prevalence and factors associated with polypharmacy: a systematic review and Meta-analysis. *BMC Geriatrics* 22(1): 601. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12877-022-03279-x>
- Doherty AS, Adamson G, Mallett J, Darcy C, McKee H, Friel A, Scott MG, Miller EFR (2025) Addressing potentially inappropriate prescribing in care homes: regional evaluation of a pharmacist-led model in Northern Ireland. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy* 47(6): 2061–2071. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-025-02031-w>
- Griese-Mammen N, Hersberger KE, Messerli M, Leikola S, Horvat N, van Mil JWF, Kos M (2018) PCNE definition of medication review: reaching agreement. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy* 40(5): 1199–1208. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-018-0696-7>
- Guillot J, Maumus-Robert S, Bezin J (2020) Polypharmacy: A general review of definitions, descriptions and determinants. *Therapie* 75(5): 407–416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.therap.2019.10.001>
- Huong DTL, Hang NT, Ly NK, Nhat NH, Huong NTL, Hue LTP, Anh DTL, Dung BTK, Phuong PM, Lan LT, Tung TT, Hieu NN, Ly NH (2023) Determination of drug-related problems among type 2 diabetes outpatients in a hospital in Vietnam: A cross-sectional study. *PLOS ONE* 18(8): e0289825. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0289825>
- IBM Corporation (2024) IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 30.0. Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.
- Kim J, Parish AL (2017) Polypharmacy and medication management in older adults. *Nursing Clinics of North America* 52(3): 457–468. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cnur.2017.04.007>
- Kovačević T, Falade J (2025) Overcoming challenges: implementing and scaling clinical pharmacy education and practice in the Republic of Srpska/Bosnia and Herzegovina. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy* 47: 1526–1531. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-025-01939-7>
- Kovačević T, Savić Davidović M, Barišić V, Fazlić E, Miljković S, Djajić V, Miljković B, Kovačević P (2024) The role of a clinical pharmacist in the identification of potentially inadequate drugs prescribed to the geriatric population in low-resource settings using the beers criteria: A pilot study. *Pharmacy* 12(3): 84. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmacy12030084>
- Lenßen R, Heidenreich A, Schulz JB, Trautwein C, Fitzner C, Jaehde U, Eisert A (2016) Analysis of drug-related problems in three departments of a German University hospital. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy* 38(1): 119–126. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-015-0213-1>
- Madeira D, Baduy F, Orfão A, Matos C, Osório R, Brito AC (2023) One size does not fit all: Medication reconciliation and review at the hospital at home. *Cureus* 15(10): e47419. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.47419>
- Ma Z, Sun S, Zhang C, Yuan X, Chen Q, Wu J, Wang X, Liu L (2021) Characteristics of drug-related problems and pharmacists' interventions in a geriatric unit in China. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy* 43(1): 270–274. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-020-01128-8>

- Marković-Peković V, Škrbić R, Godman B, Gustafsson LL (2012) Ongoing initiatives in the Republic of Srpska to enhance prescribing efficiency: influence and future directions. *Expert Review of Pharmacoeconomics & Outcomes Research* 12(5): 661–671. <https://doi.org/10.1586/erp.12.48>
- Marković-Peković V, Škrbić R, Petrović A, Vlahović-Palčevski V, Mrak J, Bennie M, Fadare J, Kwon HY, Schiffers K, Truter I, Godman B (2016) Polypharmacy among the elderly in the Republic of Srpska: extent and implications for the future. *Expert Review of Pharmacoeconomics & Outcomes Research* 16(5): 609–618. <https://doi.org/10.1586/14737167.2016.1115347>
- Nielsen TR, Andersen SE, Rasmussen M, Honoré PH (2013) Clinical pharmacist service in the acute ward. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy* 35(6): 1137–1151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11096-013-9837-1>
- Ni XF, Yang CS, Bai YM, Hu ZX, Zhang LL (2021) Drug-related problems of patients in primary health care institutions: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 12: 698907. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2021.698907>
- PCNE Association [Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe Association] (2020) PCNE Classification for Drug-Related Problems V9.1. www.pcne.org/upload/files/417_PCNE_classification_V9-1_final.pdf [accessed 12 September 2025]
- Priya K, Sreshta M, Philip S (2021) Cost-saving medication therapy management for outpatients. *Perspectives in Clinical Research* 12(1): 14–20. https://doi.org/10.4103/picr.PICR_164_18
- Računari [d.o.o.] (2024) Klinički informacioni sistem – KIS. Banja Luka, Republika Srpska: Računari.
- Saldanha V, Araújo IB, Lima SIVC, Martins RR, Oliveira AG (2020) Risk factors for drug-related problems in a general hospital: A large prospective cohort. *PLOS ONE* 15(5): e0230215. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0230215>
- Schindler E, Hohmann C, Culmsee C (2020) Medication review by community pharmacists for type 2 diabetes patients in routine care: Results of the DIATHEM-study. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 11: 1176. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2020.01176>
- Smedberg J, Bråthen M, Waka MS, Jacobsen AF, Gjerdalen G, Nordeng H (2016) Medication use and drug-related problems among women at maternity wards—a cross-sectional study from two Norwegian hospitals. *European Journal of Clinical Pharmacology* 72(7): 849–857. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00228-016-2042-0>
- Stuhec M, Zorjan K (2022) Clinical pharmacist interventions in ambulatory psychogeriatric patients with excessive polypharmacy. *Scientific Reports* 12(1): 11387. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-15657-x>
- Štuhec M, Flegar I, Zelko E, Kovačič A, Zabavnik V (2021) Clinical pharmacist interventions in cardiovascular disease pharmacotherapy in elderly patients on excessive polypharmacy: A retrospective pre-post observational multicentric study. *Wiener Klinische Wochenschrift* 133(15–16): 770–779. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00508-020-01801-y>
- Subramanian A, Azcoaga-Lorenzo A, Anand A, Phillips K, Lee SI, Cockburn N, Fagbamigbe AF, Damase-Michel C, Yau C, McCowan C, O'Reilly D, Santorelli G, Hope H, Kennedy JI, Abel KM, Eastwood KA, Locock L, Black M, Loane M, Moss N, Plachcinski R, Thangaratinam S, Brophy S, Agrawal U, Vowles Z, Brocklehurst P, Dolk H, Nelson-Piercy C, Nirantharakumar K, MuM-PreDiCT Group (2023) Polypharmacy during pregnancy and associated risk factors: a retrospective analysis of 577 medication exposures among 1.5 million pregnancies in the UK, 2000–2019. *BMC Medicine* 21(1): 21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-022-02722-5>
- Su YJ, Yan YD, Wang WJ, Xu T, Gu ZC, Bai YR, Lin HW (2021) Drug-related problems among hospitalized cancer pain patients: an investigative single-arm intervention trial. *Annals of Palliative Medicine* 10(2): 2008–2017. <https://doi.org/10.21037/apm-20-1458>
- Tan EC, Stewart K, Elliott RA, George J (2014) Pharmacist consultations in general practice clinics: the Pharmacists in Practice Study (PIPS). *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy* 10(4): 623–632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2013.08.005>
- Tay HY, Islahudin F, Siaw YY, Wong WC, Mohd Tahir NA, Firdaus Khan SS (2024) Drug-related problems among peritoneal dialysis patients: A 12-year retrospective cohort study. *Cureus* 16(9): e69700. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.69700>
- Thompson R, Whennan L, Liang J, Alderman C, Grzeskowiak LE (2015) Investigating the frequency and nature of medication-related problems in the women's health unit of an Australian tertiary teaching hospital. *Annals of Pharmacotherapy* 49(7): 770–776. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1060028015581009>
- Urbańczyk K, Guntschnig S, Antoniadis V, Falamic S, Kovacevic T, Kurczewska-Michalak M, Miljković B, Olearova A, Sviestina I, Szucs A, Tachkov K, Tiszai Z, Volmer D, Wiela-Hojeńska A, Fialova D, Vlcek J, Stuhec M, Hogg A, Scott M, Stewart D, Mair A, Ravera S, Lery FX, Kardas P (2023) Recommendations for wider adoption of clinical pharmacy in Central and Eastern Europe in order to optimise pharmacotherapy and improve patient outcomes. *Frontiers in Pharmacology* 14: 1244151. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2023.1244151>
- Vale Bezerra PK, Chaves Cavalcanti JE, Carlete Filho SR, Medeiros SDV, Oliveira AG, Martins RR (2023) Drug-related problems in hypertension and gestational diabetes mellitus: A hospital cohort. *PLOS ONE* 18(4): e0284053. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0284053>
- Westerlund T, Marklund B (2009) Assessment of the clinical and economic outcomes of pharmacy interventions in drug-related problems. *Journal of Clinical Pharmacy and Therapeutics* 34(3): 319–327. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2710.2008.01017.x>
- World Health Organization (2019) Medication safety in polypharmacy: technical report. Geneva: WHO. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/325454/WHO-UHC-SDS-2019.11-eng.pdf?sequence=1> [accessed 08 August 2025]
- Yates L, Valente M, Wadsworth C (2020) Evaluation of pharmacist medication review service in an outpatient heart failure clinic. *Journal of Pharmacy Practice* 33(6): 820–826. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0897190019842696>
- Zafar R, Rehman IU, Shah Y, Ming LC, Goh KW, Suleiman AK, Khan TM (2025) Impact of pharmacist-led intervention for reducing drug-related problems and improving quality of life among chronic kidney disease patients: A randomized controlled trial. *PLOS ONE* 20(2): e0317734. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0317734>
- Zhang S, Zhang GB, Huang P, Ren Y, Lin B, Shao YE, Ye XL (2023) Drug-related problems in hospitalized patients with chronic kidney diseases and clinical pharmacist interventions. *BMC Geriatrics* 23(1): 849. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12877-023-04557-y>